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The effect of dust accumulation and cleaning methods on PV panels' outcomes based on an experimental study of six locations in Northern Oman

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Abstract

The Sultanate of Oman, similar to other GCC countries, is affected by the fluctuation of oil prices, which led the decision-makers in this country to move towards renewable energy and particularly the establishment of photovoltaic (PV) solar power plants. This step requires a thorough study before spending millions of dollars to build such power plants. Since dust is one of the main problems of PV in the GCC countries, this study investigates the influence of certain weather factors such as wind speed, relative humidity on dust accumulation and the effect of the cleaning method applied to each city separately.

After a full year of observation and data collection on climatic conditions and the output of the six systems installed and used in this study, it is found that the cities of Liwa and Sohar, followed by Muscat, exhibit the highest percentage of dust and contaminants. The most prominent pollutants are the particulate matters (PM) from the chimneys of the power plants, and smelters in the industrial city of Sohar. Also, the movement of a considerable number of vehicles in Muscat caused a rise in the concentration of PM deposited on PV cells. For the other three cities (Al-Khabourh, Suwaiq, and Shinas), they are far from any industrial zone, and because of reduced traffic, the percentage of accumulation of dust and pollution of PV cells was limited.

Nine available methods have been used to clean the PV cells after the dust accumulated for one month. From these methods, it is found that the use of water is sufficient to wash the PV cells in the cities of Al-Khaburah, Shinas, and Al-Suwaiq, but the effect of cleaning is more reduced on Sohar, Liwa, and Muscat. Because of PM and many chemical compounds, the use of a sodium solution was the best option in cleaning the PV cells of these three cities. It was noted that the loss of solar cell productivity decreases during the rainy season, which acts as a natural cleaner for the PV. The study also found that dew in the cities studied before sunrise causes the interaction of some salts of sodium, magnesium, and calcium and builds a layer of cohesive salts, which are difficult to clean.

Keywords: Photovoltaic; Solar; dust; PM; cleaning methods; Northern Oman.

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INTRODUCTION

Oman is one of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries and is located in the Middle East within the solar belt and owns one of the most significant solar radiation intensity value in the world. The Sultanate is characterised by being close to the desert of Saudi Arabia, bordered by the north and west, and south by the Arabian Sea and the Indian Ocean. This region is characterised by high atmospheric temperatures most of the year and high atmospheric dust concentrations. In the last few years, the GCC and Sultanate have suffered from extreme fluctuations in oil prices, while the climate change phenomena have affected the country (Al-Maamari et al., 2017). From the womb of these problems, the Sultanate has produced an ambitious program for all GCC countries to switch to solar energy in generating electricity, especially using PV cells (Al-Maamari et al., 2016). This technology is reliable; it does not depend on moving parts and does not produce any air contaminants or noise. It is environmentally friendly, flexible in various areas of the atmosphere and topography, and does not require heavy but rather low-cost maintenance. PV cells rely on sunlight as fuel and thus consume free fuel and are available most of the year (Babatunde et al., 2018).

With the apparent advances in PV technology and the low cost of producing electricity using these panels, which have reached less than 2 ct/kWh, solar energy will become the cheapest electricity producer in different regions of the world (Ilsea et al., 2018). As is known, the presence of these PV cells exposed to different weather conditions makes them vulnerable to external weather factors such as the solar radiation intensity, atmospheric temperature, relative humidity, and wind (Babattab et al., 2016). These factors may cause low energy production from the PV cell, and the problem consists in the overlap effects of these factors with each other. While high solar radiation causes a rise in the temperature of the cell because the more significant part thereof serves this purpose, the more the temperature of the air reduces the heat transfer from the PV cell to the hot air outside, and as a result, lower cell efficiency is achieved. Areas with high solar radiation intensity (such as those within the global solar belt) suffer from high concentrations of airborne dust, resulting mainly from desert dust. The accumulation of dust on the surface of the PV cell significantly reduces the cell's performance, especially in deserts whose natural cleaning is confined to the rain (which is generally low) and high winds (Quan et al., 2017). Regular cleaning is used to reduce energy loss due to pollution. In this instant, cleaning costs will be added, which may cause higher expenses compared to the grid electricity produced, and more difficult if these panels were installed in water-scarce areas such as desert areas (Miller et al., 2016; Kazem et al., 2015).

The coastal areas of Oman are characterised by high relative humidity most of the year. Relative humidity is defined as the ratio of water vapour pressure in the air at a certain temperature to the vapour pressure of saturation at this temperature (Figgis et al., 2018). High relative humidity causes capillary adhesion between dust particles and surfaces (Naushevsky et al., 2017) when the capillary adhesion prevails; it excels other adhesion mechanisms as the van der Waals force, so the deposition and accumulation of dust have a strong relationship to the atmospheric relative humidity. High humidity results in dewdrop especially early in the morning on PV surfaces. These droplets cover particles of dust deposited on the surface of the cell, interact with water-soluble compounds, and when the water droplet evaporated the soluble materials are deposited on the surface of the PV cell (Yilbas et al., 2015; Hassan et al., 2016; Hinds, 2012). The Sultanate's view on the Indian Ocean makes the air humidity full of sodium chloride (NaCl). This material has a significant effect on water absorption, so when it is within the chemical composition of the dust particles and pollutants accumulated on the surface of the PV cell, the water droplets will be filled with sodium chloride that enters the cell

cracks. When water evaporates, sodium chloride is left in these cracks and on the surface (Balarew, 1987). Lombardo et al., (2010) demonstrated that magnesium salts ($MgSO_4$ and $MgCl_2$) have the same properties as NaCl. Sulphur and nitrate salts from water-soluble nuclei and naturally increase the contamination on the surface of the PV cells. When the water evaporates, these salts crystallise and form in the folds, cracks, and surface of the PV cells. Sulphate ions (SO_2) and nitrates (NO_3) are present in the air and are caused by sea spray and industrial processes (Jentzsch et al., 2013; Boyle et al., 2016). Pollutants from burning fossil fuels, especially PM10, are in their chemical composition sulfuric compounds, so part of them dissolve in surface moisture and increase adhesion to surface pollutants (Figgis, 2016; Kazem et al., 2017). Kazem et al., (2017) showed that the cleanliness index (a measure of loss due to pollution) is closely linked to PM10 concentrations, wind speed, and relative humidity of the atmosphere. High levels of PM10 in the air cause a decrease in the cleanliness index (increased cell surface pollution), especially at relatively low winds and humidity. In the case of wind speed higher than 4 m/s and relative humidity higher than 65%, the effect of PM10 was slight. The authors emphasised that wind speed and relative humidity are useful in determining the amount of dust accumulated on the surface of the PV cells and its electrical power production.

Wind is another factor that affects the PV cells performance. Increased wind speed for more than 3 m/s causes dust and sand to rise in the desert, reducing the solar radiation reaching the PV cells and reducing its productivity (Oguntoke et al., 2013). If the direction of the wind faces the surface of the PV cells, the movement of air will remove some of the dust particles accumulated on it. On the other hand, the dust rising in the air because of the wind with very small diameters will remain stuck in the air and after the drop of wind speed will deposit and accumulate on the surface of the PV cells. Gholami et al., (2017) found that for such cases the amount of dust collected higher than those removed, which means a high density of accumulated dust. Wind speed increases the cooling of the PV cells and reduces its temperature. It also reduces the relative humidity of the air and thus reduces its damage. Ref. (Gholami et al., 2017) clarified that the critical levels that determine the accumulation of massive amounts of dust on the PV cells are the average wind velocity above 4 m/s and the relative humidity is less than 50%. In order to solve the significant overlap between the external factors affecting the accumulation of dust on the PV cells. Bi et al., (2013) sought to measure clean and dusty samples under the same conditions and at the same time, so in this case, the only variable is the accumulation of dust on the PV cells surface and neutralisation of other climatic conditions. Kazem et al. (2017) concluded that the positive wind effect on the PV cells is higher when the relative humidity is low, but when it is higher than 50%, the wind effect becomes negative.

The low productivity of the PV cells due to the accumulation of dust depends not only on the amount of accumulated dust but also on the physical and chemical dust composition (Saidan et al., 2016; Sarver et al., 2013; Kazem et al., 2016; Fujiwara et al., 2011), which varies by region. Ta et al. (2004) manifested that the primary source of dust in the hot and desert areas is the soil, while in the cities the accumulated dust comes from other sources such as engine exhausts and power station chimneys in addition to the volatilisation of different building materials. In the arid and semi-arid regions, most of the accumulated dust is natural, and this ratio is sometimes affected by seasons. Ferrada et al. (2015) showed that part of the pollutants sometimes come from the remains of birds, plant residues, soot, and organic matter.

PV cells inclination directly affects the amount of accumulated dust. The lower the cell's tendency, the higher the amount of dust collected. In areas north of the equator (such as Oman) PV cells are installed facing south and at a tilt

angle equal to the latitude of this region, and sometimes depending on the radiation data of the region the angle of inclination is increased to be equal to the latitude + 2.8° (Lu et al., 2017; Ghazi et al., 2014). Ghazi et al. (2014) demonstrated that the worst degree of tendency of the PV cells, which multiplies the accumulation of dust, is to stabilise the cell by horizontal position (Moharram et al., 2013). Oman is located at latitudes 18 to 23 north of the equator, making the cell's tilt angle low and causing a rise in accumulated dust.

Many research studies published in literature have shown the effect of dust accumulation and its negative effects on cell productivity. This study presents some of the results of practical research that measured the degradation of PV production in Oman and the GCC. Kazem et al. (2014) studied the effect of cleaning PV cells after 45 days without cleaning on their electrical output. Non-cleaning PV cells cause their electrical efficiency to decrease from 16% to 8% over 45 days. After the required cleaning of the PV cells using water mixed with ionic and cationic material, the cell recovered its initial efficiency (16%). In Iraq, Chaichan et al. (2015) reviewed all the circumstances that caused the transformation of the fertile Mesopotamia to the source basin of dust, sand, and dust storms for the whole region. The study showed the country's need for PV systems to meet the growing need for electricity, and the reason for the reluctance of decision-makers to resort to the use of this technique is the abundance of dusty days throughout the country. Saidan et al. (2016) studied the effect of dust and vehicles accumulation on installed cells near a highway in the Iraqi capital Baghdad. The PV cells productivity was reduced by 12% after two months of cell work without cleaning. The researchers also explained that cleaning the cell with a substance containing sodium gives better results than cleaning it with water or rain. The effect of dust on the efficiency of PV cells tested in Baghdad - Iraq was found to be less than 6.24% after 1 day, 11.8% after one week without cleaning, and 18.74% after one month without cleaning (Chaichan et al., 2018; Javad et al., 2017). A detailed study on the effect of dust accumulation on PV cells and modern methods of cleaning, and at the end of the chapter on the subject the authors stated that the use of these cells in Iraq is possible only with the concern of periodic cleaning in the appropriate manner.

In Qatar, Fountoukis et al. (2018) studied the size of the dust particles accumulated on the PV cells installed in the capital city of Doha, and the impact of exposure time on these volumes. The results of the study indicate that the accumulation of small-size particles causes greater degradation than large-scale particles to cause the system's performance even though they are together from the same mass of dust, because the small particles are distributed more regularly on the surface of the PV cells and thus the surface area becomes more massive than the coarse molecules. Javed et al. (2017) also show a nonlinear relationship between the loss of PV cells productivity and the amount of accumulated dust and relative humidity. This result was obtained after a 12-month study in an arid environment in Qatar, during which data were taken of solar radiation, dust concentrations, and meteorological data. Figgis et al. (2017) collected the dust accumulated on the solar cells in the city of Doha for ten months and sorted by the accumulation rate of dust and changed the index of cleanliness. The results of the study showed that dust accumulates at an average volume of 260 mg/m² after exposure for one week, 2170 mg/m² each month, and 14,547 mg/m² every six months. These results also showed that the volume of the accumulated particles and the average amount of accumulated dust decreased with increasing exposure time. The cleanliness factor of the PV cells is linked to the rate of accumulation of dust with an inverse relationship.

Figgis (2016) studied the relationship between wind velocity and dust deposition rate on an oil-rich collector fixed on a building in Qatar. The study showed that sedimentation is the most critical factor in the accumulation of dust on the

surface of the collector if the wind speed is less than 3 m/s. The effect of relative humidity and dew rate on the accumulation of dust in the desert areas of Qatar was found by Ilse et al. (2016). The relative humidity in the night of Qatar was less than the morning in an average of 13-22%, which means that in the best months of the year (August and September); the dew will be formed on the surface of the PV cells in the night and early morning. The process of forming dew on the accumulated dust enhances the adhesion to the cell surface and depending on the chemical dust composition; it may be doubled the strength of this adhesion (Ilse et al., 2018). In his study of the causes of the accumulation of dust on PV cells in Doha, Qatar, Tanesab et al. (2017) showed that the dust deposition process, its adhesion, and removal are directly related to factors such as wind speed, relative humidity, temperature and above all the concentration of PM.

In Saudi Arabia, Adinoyi et al. (2013) studied the relationship between the accumulation of dust and the tilt angle of the PV cells and found that the amount of accumulated dust decreased by increasing the cell tilt angle. Al Shehri et al. (2016) confirmed that the exposure of the PV cells in the eastern part of Saudi Arabia (near the Arabian Gulf) for six months to air without cleaning caused the loss of 50% of the product of the cell. Emziane et al. (2015) studied the effect of dust accumulation on light transmittance for some samples in the Arabian desert in Saudi Arabia and found that the light permeability was reduced to 84% due to dust. The researchers demonstrated the possibility of restoring the permeability by washing and wiping while when using the brush didn't achieve the desired benefit.

In the United Arab Emirates, the northern neighbour of Oman, El-Nashar (1994) studied the effect of dust accumulation for a whole year on the cleanliness factor for variable types of PV cells; the study concluded that the multi-crystalline panels have the best cleanliness factor. Hadwan et al. (2016) studied the impact of dust accumulation in the UAE on glass permeability and PV cells efficiency. The researchers concluded that dust accumulation reduces glass permeability by 10% and cell efficiency by 70%. As for Yemen, the southern neighbor of Oman, the impact of the using multiple PV cells technologies on desert and rural communities in this country has been studied by Charabi et al. (2013). The study showed that these technologies offer a competitive and promising alternative that can impact the economies of these regions.

In Oman, the PV cells technology has been very interested in preparing for the future of these cells at the public and government levels. Therefore, there are many important studies in this field. Kazem et al. (2014) studied the effect of dust and temperature on the efficiency of PV cells in Oman. The researchers found that only 9% of the area of Oman is suitable for the deployment of PV systems. This area is characterised by moderate temperatures and low atmospheric and metallic pollutants. While Kazem et al. (2013) demonstrated that the cleanliness coefficient of PV cells installed on the roof of a building in Oman was up to 21%. As for the PV cells established in the desert of Oman, Kazem (2011) explained that the low power produced from the cells depends precisely on the quality of the accumulated dust and the level of this accumulation. Among the studied dust pollutants (sand, calcium carbonate, silica, red soil, and ash), it was found that the ash accumulation was the most influential on PV cells productivity, with a lower voltage of 25% compared to a clear cell. Fujiwara et al. (2011) studied the influence of the physical properties of accumulated dust from different areas of northern Oman. The researchers found that the most significant loss of electrical efficiency was up to 0.05% per day with deterioration in PV cells productivity from 30 to 40% over three months without cleaning. All researchers confirm that the method and time of periodic cleaning PV cells is of great importance in recovering all or a large part of the power lost due to accumulation of dust and dirt. Many of the cleaning techniques have been

mentioned in the literature ranging from manual techniques to complex robot-based techniques. These techniques are characterised by their ability according to the environment and climatic conditions. Some of them have proved to be unsuitable for the desert climates (such as the current study area) as it requires intensive use of water, which is rare in such areas.

Al-Housani et al. (2019) have practically studied several techniques to clean PV cells in desert climates. For better analysis, the researchers studied cleaning efficiency (energy output change in W and %), cleaning frequency (daily, weekly, monthly), total cleaning cost (USD/m²), power consumption, and weight. Selected cleaning techniques were studied, such as cloth wipers, brushes, vacuum cleaners, and some combinations. The optimum cleaning period for each technique was studied over time periods ranging from one day, one week to one month. The results of the study show a significant reduction in the efficiency of PV systems for monthly cleaning periods regardless of cleaning technique in desert climatic conditions. The results showed that using fibre-based cloth scanner is the most cost-effective and performance-oriented technology. Regular weekly cleaning gave the best results at the lowest cost.

Many researchers have used more complex techniques such as electric curtain technology to clean PV panels during which an electric wave is used to create a travel wave that prevents any dust molecule from stabilising on the surface of the solar panel (Calle et al., 2009). This technique is expensive, as well as there are many safety concerns during rainy days. There is also a modern method of painting surfaces of PV panels with anti-dust materials, namely self-cleaning nanoparticles (super-hydrophilicity and super-hydrophobic films). Many studies proved that using the TiO₂ film is a very clean method, but it requires water, so this technique is not suitable for desert climates (Isaifan et al., 2017; Zhong et al., 2017).

In this study, the effect of dust type and its accumulated mass on the performance of photovoltaic cells will be studied in six selected areas of Oman. The study will cover the overlapping effects of weather factors that distinguish these areas separately with their contaminants and their impact on the performance of photovoltaic cells in these areas. There is a broad plan to reach the Sultanate of Oman to produce 20 to 30% of its electricity from photovoltaic power plants, and the need for detailed data and information for each part of the Sultanate. In this study, some of these data, which focus on the effect of weather variables on the performance of photovoltaic cells established in these cities or will be established. We will also focus on the proper cleaning methods and the time needed for periodic cleaning of the cells to continue their work efficiently. Researchers hope that the information obtained in this study will be useful in determining the future of photovoltaic cells in these areas.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3. Studied region

The Sultanate of Oman is situated in the south-eastern corner of the Arabian Peninsula in Southwest Asia. Oman is found between scopes 16° 40' and 26° 20' north and longitudes 51° 50' and 59° 40' east (Dorlvlo et al., 1998). The coastline of the Sultanate stretches out for 3165 km from the Strait of Hormuz in the north and finishes at Ras Darbat Ali close to the Republic of Yemen outskirts in the south (Al-Badi, 2009). Sultanate of Oman map is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Oman's aggregate populace in 2010 was 3,174,000. The aggregate number of lodging units in this nation is roughly 540,770. This number incorporates singular houses and flats in structures. The aggregate land region of Oman

is 309,500 km², and the populace thickness is 9.3 occupants per km². The yearly populace development rate is roughly 4.4% (Kazem et al., 2013). A large portion of the populace approaches power; in any case, a few people in rural and remote territories experience issues getting to the electric grid (Babatunde et al., 2018).

Solar energy vitality is a spotless and accessible wellspring of vitality for electrical power production in rural and remote zones, which has been affirmed by numerous published critical studies (Al-Badi, 2018). The vast majority of the investigations proposed PV power plants as the most reasonable strategy for creating electric power in these regions (Kazem, 2011). Oman is described by its clear skies (around 342 days/year). Also, as a nation situated in the Sun Belt, its land area takes into consideration a high sun-oriented vitality potential. Inappropriately, the more significant part of the country and remote territories are desert zones in which dust storms happen for most of the year. Residue testimony on PV panels lessens the produced power and causes PV execution corruption.

Fig. 1 Sultanate of Oman map [1].

This investigation has concentrated on the “Al-Batina” and “Muscat” districts, which are in the north of the Sultanate of Oman and comprise 12 areas where 55% of the Sultanate of Oman subjects live. The two most prominent industrial regions are likewise in this locale. The investigation region incorporates the accompanying regions: Shinas (24° 44' N, 56° 27' E), Liwa (24° 30' N, 56° 34' E), Sohar (24° 21' N, 56° 42' E), Al-Khabourah (23° 59' N, 57° 05'), Al-Suwaiq (23° 50' N, 57° 26' E) and Muscat (23° 36' N, 58° 35' E) as shown in Fig. 1. This region lies on the coast in the north of Sultanate of Oman.

4. Experimental setup

To conduct and investigate the PV performance in the studied regions, six identical systems were designed and installed in these cities. Figure 2 illustrates the experimental setup. The system contains the following parts:

- A two-identical monocrystalline silicon PV panel is a 125 W maximum power, 21.8 V open circuit voltage, 7.45 A short circuit current, 3.5 kg, and 1.43 m length × 0.63 m width × 0.9 m² areas. One PV is clean, and the other one is dusty for comparison purposes.
- Digital Voltmeter-Ammeter, voltage: DC 0-100 V, current: 0-10 A, dual display, brand name: “HAILANGNIAO”.
- Solar radiation transmitter detector (4-20 ma), range 0-1500 W/m², brand name: “WE300”
- Back panel temperature sensor, brand name: “WE710”.
- Relative humidity and air temperature sensors “RHT2nl-02”. RH accuracy 2%. Precision Thermistor Temp Sensor (+/-0.1 °C, 0 to 70 °C) with non-linear output.
- Wind speed and direction anemometer, range 0-30 m/s, accuracy: +- (0.3+0.03v) m/s, brand name: “MoreSunsDIY”.

To investigate the impact of the dust on the electrical parameters as well as the performance of the PV panel, environmental parameters are taken in consideration separately and mixed. The observation of the daily climatic conditions was continued for one year. The outputs of the PV cells (current and voltage) were read weekly and recorded. On the 29th day, the PV cells were cleaned. The PV cells used in the study were cleaned with nine specific cleaning methods at the end of the month. In the last three months, the PV cells were cleaned with water, but the cleaning process was done at different times (evening, early morning and afternoon) to study the effect of dew on the cells. The study was conducted from 1 November 2017 to 31 October 2018.

The people participating in PV cleaning were trained on cleaning procedures so that they adopted the same procedure to reduce human factor.

Fig. 2 Experimental setup.

Results and Discussions

The variable weather conditions during the year have a significant impact on the accumulated dust on the PV panels regarding quantity and quantity. Therefore, Fig. 3 shows the monthly mean of solar radiation, temperature, wind speed and relative humidity for a year for a full year starting from 1 November 2017 until 31 October 2018.

It is noticeable from the figure that the solar radiation of the study area is convergent throughout the year, which is in the average high value and causes large heating of the PV cells and without cooling it, its electrical output will be reduced. In general, this is now a simple issue with the use of photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) systems. The temperatures in the study area are generally moderate and on average no more than 35°C. The studied area is characterised by low temperature at night below the dew point, which makes the dew on the surfaces of PV cells, stressing during night and before sunrise.

The wind speed of the study area is low for most hours of the day except in the afternoon, as it rises somewhat. Oman's location on the Indian Ocean makes the breeze of the mainland, which is formed during the afternoon because of the high temperature of the land in exchange for a low temperature of the water with a medium speed. The highest wind speeds were recorded at Suwaiq, Shinas, and Muscat. The low wind speed helps to increase the relative humidity, and this is what happens before the sunrise and produces dew with temperatures below the dew point. Large amounts of dew, which react with the dust components and when vaporising after sunrise leave many types of salts and sulphates adhering to the surface and planks of the PV panel.

On average, the relative humidity in the study area rises before sunrise and after sunset more than the afternoon when the relative humidity decreases for two main reasons: the high temperature of the air which enables the air to carry more significant amounts of water vapour and high wind speed that reduce relative humidity. The meeting of these two factors determines the effect of relative humidity on PV cells during the afternoon, but their absence in the

evening and before sunrise makes the RH have a high impact on the cell. This effect consists of forming a layer of dew for a suitable period to interact with the chemical components of the accumulated dust and penetration of these droplets into the cracks and churns of the PV cells and then after the evaporation of the water in the morning leaving a cohesive salt layer that is difficult to clean in areas where access is difficult.

Figure 3 shows that the weather conditions of the cities are relatively close and the changes are limited. Hence, the effect of these conditions on PV cells is expected to be somewhat similar.

Figure 4 shows the monthly accumulation of dust in the studied cities. The rate of accumulation of dust in the studied cities is little compared to neighbouring countries such as the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia, as indicated by Darwish et al. (2015, 2018). The highest dust accumulation amount is in the cities of Liwa and Sohar and the lowest value in Al-Khabourah and Al-Suwaiq. The high rates of dust accumulation in Liwa and Sohar caused by proximity to the industrial zone and the port of Sohar as dust, chemical compounds and dyes, in addition to building materials in the air caused by human activities concentrated in this region. Another significant effect is the soot and particulate matters (PM) emitted from the Sohar refinery and thousands of heavy vehicles stationed in this area. The decrease in the monthly accumulation rate of dust in the Al-Khabourah and Al-Suwaiq areas is due to the absence of high human activities in these cities as being only two residential cities. Muscat is also experiencing high dust rates due to the top construction work being the capital of the country in addition to the Al-Rusail industrial zone, traffic of cars, heavy vehicles, and construction vehicles in huge numbers daily.

Fig. 3 The yearly average climatic conditions of the studied areas.

Figure 5 shows the chemical analysis of the dust components accumulated in the studied soil. Most dust components (up to 65%) are silicon oxides, the main element of desert sand. Some residues of sulphur and hydrocarbons, which consist of soot and volatile particulate matters, appear in the atmosphere. The concentrations of many components vary according to the cities, for example, the highest amount of smoke and PM appeared in Liwa followed by Sohar because of their proximity to the largest industrial area in Oman. While sodium salts, calcium and magnesium oxides were the highest recording is Al-Khabourah followed by Muscat. The source of these salts is the sea overlooking all the cities of study, but the impact of the movement of wind because of the topography of the region makes concentrations of these salts higher in these cities. The rest of the chemicals rates are small and limited and resulted from human activities, including the exhaust and wheels of cars.

Fig. 4 Monthly rate of dust accumulation on the PV surface for the studied cities

Fig. 5 Dust components of the studied cities

Figure 6 shows a magnified image using an electronic microscope of dry white paper. The top part of the contaminated PV cells it was cleaned. In these images, the particles in white represent silica particles, while the particles in the black colour represent the soot and PM. Yellow and green coloured particles represent metal particles. We notice from the photos that Liwa and Sohar have a high percentage of smoke and PM while it is lower in the rest of the cities, which shows the significant impact of the industrial zone and the port in addition to the power plant in Sohar province. The mineral pollutants (yellow and green) are also increasing in Sohar and Liwa, and the effect of mineral plants and

factories is evident in the industrial zone adjacent to them. The materials in the photographs taken to the rest of the cities are less critical because of their distance from the industrial zones.

Fig. 6 The accumulated dust quality on filters for the studied cities (a) Shinas, (b) Liwa, (c) Sohar, (d) Al-Khabourah, (e) Al-Suwaiq, and (f) Muscat.

Figure 7 shows the effect of the accumulation of dust on the PV cells as a reduction of its electrical efficiency. The decrease in efficiency is from 5.5% (Al-Suwaiq and Al-Khabourah) to 18% (Liwa). The highest monthly decline in electricity productivity was for the city of Liwa followed by Sohar and Muscat. Air pollution due to the industrial port in Sohar and the movement of the heavy vehicle in Muscat has doubled the impact of accumulated dust. Although the weather conditions are similar to the cities chosen in the study, the quality of the dust and the overlap of some of the weather variables caused less electrical efficiency of the Liwa and Sohar than the rest of the cities. The decrease in cell electrical productivity for the period from May to September is due to the presence of other factors that must be taken into account, namely, the high intensity of solar radiation during this period to reach the maximum and the high temperature of the atmosphere in the summer. The reduction in the decrease rate at winter season (December and January) can be referred to the rain that washes the PV panels doing natural cleaning.

Fig. 7 Reduction in PV output efficiencies for the studied cities

Figure 8 shows the effect of cleaning materials used on the rate of decrease in electric power generated per month. Failure to clean the PV panel for a month reduces the production capacity to a high rate up to 50% and higher sometimes. Cleaning PV panels with water only reduce the rate of decrease in generated power in non-industrial cities such as Al-Khaburah, Suwaiq, and Shinas but have limited impact on other cities with high air pollution. The uses of glass razor, squeegee, velour, and sponge have a limited impact on the power reduction rate demonstrating its failure to clean the PV panels. Using detergents in cleaning the PV panel can be a better choice but using sodium detergent has given a higher impact on the reduction power rate especially for the industrial cities. Sodium detergent was advised by Saidan et al. (2016), it can treat chemicals such as PM, soot, magnesium and calcium oxides and NaCl.

Fig. 8 The impact of cleaning tools and chemicals on the PV power reduction rate

Dew consists on the surface of PV panels with low temperature at night and high atmospheric relative humidity for most of the year for the cities studied. Dew drops interact with the salts deposited on the PV panel and dissolve these salts, making it possible to enter the cracks. At sunrise the water evaporates and remains the salts forming a solid layer on the surface of the cell in several areas of it and this layer prevents the arrival of sunlight to the cell, and it is a factor in increasing the temperature of the cell, causing a significant loss of power produced. Figure 9 shows the effect of cell cleaning time on the water on the ratio of lost capacity. The results of the study show that the best time to clean the cell is evening because of the process of disposal of salts before interaction with dew drops. The difference in the loss ratio shows little if the cleaning was done every month, but if the process was done in a shorter period, the effect would be much better.

Fig. 9 cleaning time influence on power reduction rate for the studied cities

Conclusions

The accumulation of dust in desert or semi-desert areas is one of the most critical problems that delay the spread of PV cells in these areas. The study site (northern Oman) is located southeast of the Arabian Peninsula, a massive area of extending desert. If we add to this factor the movement of vehicles and heavy trucks and the presence of large power stations in addition to industrial cities, we find that the study of the accumulation of dust and pollutants on PV panels is necessary to ensure the establishment of plants work efficiently in this region.

This study presented, observations, and collection of data for weather conditions, dust and pollutants accumulated in six cities located north of Oman. The chemical components of accumulated dust were studied and analysed, and the influence of wind velocity and relative humidity on the collected dust type on the PV cells was examined. The reduction of hydrocarbons accumulated on the panels installed in the cities of Al-Khabourah, Suwaiq, and Shinas made cleaning the cells with water or soap solutions sufficient to restore the lost power due to the accumulation of dust and dirt. The presence of a high percentage of PM in the dust and pollutants accumulated in the cities of Liwa, Sohar, and Muscat make the cleaning process need to use sodium solutions to reach the least loss of power generated by these cells. The study found that the dew in the early morning hours of most of the year causes the interaction of water droplets with

the accumulated salts and then forming cohesive layers after evaporation of water in the morning, which are difficult to clean, especially in the slots inside the panels. The study concluded that cleaning the PV panels in the evening will avoid the formation of this layer and reduce the loss of output to the lowest levels.

Conflict of Interests

"The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper."

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References

- Al-Housani, M., Bicer, Y., Koç, M. (2019). Experimental investigations on PV cleaning of large-scale solar power plants in desert climates: Comparison of cleaning techniques for drone retrofitting. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 185, 800–815.
- Al-Maamary, H. M., Kazem, H. A., & Chaichan, M. T. (2017). The impact of oil price fluctuations on common renewable energies in GCC countries. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 75, 989-1007.
- Al-Maamary, H. M., Kazem, H. A., & Chaichan, M. T. (2017). Climate change: the game changer in the Gulf Cooperation Council region. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 76, 555-576.
- Al-Maamary, H. M., Kazem, H. A., & Chaichan, M. T. (2016). Changing the energy profile of the GCC States: A review. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research (IJAER)*, 11(3), 1980-1988.
- Al-Badi, A. H. (2018). Measured performance evaluation of a 1.4 kW grid connected desert type PV in Oman. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 47, 107-113.
- Al-Badi, A. H., Malik, A., & Gastli, A. (2009). Assessment of renewable energy resources potential in Oman and identification of barrier to their significant utilization. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 13(9), 2734-2739.
- Adinoyi, M. J., & Said, S. A. (2013). Effect of dust accumulation on the power outputs of solar photovoltaic modules. *Renewable energy*, 60, 633-636.
- Al Shehri, A., Parrott, B., Carrasco, P., Al Saiari, H., & Taie, I. (2016). Impact of dust deposition and brush-based dry cleaning on glass transmittance for PV modules applications. *Solar Energy*, 135, 317-324.
- Bi, X., Liang, S., & Li, X. (2013). A novel in situ method for sampling urban soil dust: particle size distribution, trace metal concentrations, and stable lead isotopes. *Environmental pollution*, 177, 48-57.
- Boyle, L., Flinchpaugh, H., & Hannigan, M. (2016). Assessment of PM dry deposition on solar energy harvesting systems: measurement–model comparison. *Aerosol Science and Technology*, 50(4), 380-391.

- Balarew, C. (1987). Evaporite minerals succession. *Crystal Research and Technology*, 22(10), 1241-1248.
- Babatunde, A. A., Abbasoglu, S., & Senol, M. (2018). Analysis of the impact of dust, tilt angle and orientation on performance of PV Plants. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 90, 1017-1026.
- Bahattab, M. A., Alhomoudi, I. A., Alhussaini, M. I., Mirza, M., Hegmann, J., Glaubitt, W., & Löbmann, P. (2016). Anti-soiling surfaces for PV applications prepared by sol-gel processing: Comparison of laboratory testing and outdoor exposure. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 157, 422-428.
- Calle, C. I., Buhler, C. R., McFall, J. L., Snyder, S. J., (2009). Particle removal by electrostatic and dielectrophoretic forces for dust control during lunar exploration missions. *J Electrostat*, 67, pp. 89-92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ELSTAT.2009.02.012>.
- Chaichan, M. T., & Kazem, H. A. (2018). *Generating Electricity Using Photovoltaic Solar Plants in Iraq*. Springer.
- Chaichan, M. T., Mohammed, B. A., & Kazem, H. A. (2015). Effect of pollution and cleaning on photovoltaic performance based on experimental study. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 6(4), 594-601.
- Charabi, Y., & Gastli, A. (2013). Integration of temperature and dust effects in siting large PV power plant in hot arid area. *Renewable energy*, 57, 635-644.
- Dorvlo, A. S., & Ampratwum, D. B. (1998). Summary climatic data for solar technology development in Oman. *Renewable Energy*, 14(1-4), 255-262.
- Darwish, Z. A., Kazem, H. A., Sopian, K., Al-Goul, M. A., & Alawadhi, H. (2015). Effect of dust pollutant type on photovoltaic performance. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 41, 735-744.
- Darwish, Z. A., Kazem, H. A., Sopian, K., Alghoul, M. A., & Alawadhi, H. (2018). Experimental investigation of dust pollutants and the impact of environmental parameters on PV performance: an experimental study. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 20(1), 155-174.
- Emziane, M., & Al Ali, M. (2015). Performance assessment of rooftop PV systems in Abu Dhabi. *Energy and Buildings*, 108, 101-105.
- El-Nashar, A. M. (1994). The effect of dust accumulation on the performance of evacuated tube collectors. *Solar Energy*, 53(1), 105-115.
- Figgis, B., Ennaoui, A., Ahzi, S., & Rémond, Y. (2017). Review of PV soiling particle mechanics in desert environments. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 76, 872-881.
- Figgis, B. Solar Test Facility in Doha, Qatar. doi: (<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21049.77925>).
- Ferrada, P., Araya, F., Marzo, A., & Fuentealba, E. (2015). Performance analysis of photovoltaic systems of two different technologies in a coastal desert climate zone of Chile. *Solar Energy*, 114, 356-363.
- Fujiwara, F., Rebagliati, R. J., Dawidowski, L., Gómez, D., Polla, G., Pereyra, V., & Smichowski, P. (2011). Spatial and chemical patterns of size fractionated road dust collected in a megacity. *Atmospheric Environment*, 45(8), 1497-1505.
- Fountoukis, C., Figgis, B., Ackermann, L., & Ayoub, M. A. (2018). Effects of atmospheric dust deposition on solar PV energy production in a desert environment. *Solar Energy*, 164, 94-100.
- Figgis, B. (2016, August). Role of Moisture in PV Soiling. In *Webinar, PVQAT Conf.,# TG12-2*.

- Figgis, B., Nouviaire, A., Wubulikasimu, Y., Javed, W., Guo, B., Ait-Mokhtar, A., ... & Ennaoui, A. (2018). Investigation of factors affecting condensation on soiled PV modules. *Solar Energy*, *159*, 488-500.
- Ghazi, S., Sayigh, A., & Ip, K. (2014). Dust effect on flat surfaces—A review paper. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *33*, 742-751.
- Gholami, A., Saboonchi, A., & Alemrajabi, A. A. (2017). Experimental study of factors affecting dust accumulation and their effects on the transmission coefficient of glass for solar applications. *Renewable Energy*, *112*, 466-473.
- Gholami, A., Alemrajabi, A. A., & Saboonchi, A. (2017). Experimental study of self-cleaning property of titanium dioxide and nanospray coatings in solar applications. *Solar Energy*, *157*, 559-565.
- Hassan, G., Yilbas, B. S., Said, S. A., Al-Aqeeli, N., & Matin, A. (2016). Chemo-mechanical characteristics of mud formed from environmental dust particles in humid ambient air. *Scientific reports*, *6*, 30253.
- Hadwan, M., & Alkholidi, A. (2016). Solar power energy solutions for Yemeni rural villages and desert communities. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *57*, 838-849.
- Hinds, W. C. (2012). *Aerosol technology: properties, behavior, and measurement of airborne particles*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Ilse, K., Werner, M., Naumann, V., Figgis, B. W., Hagendorf, C., & Bagdahn, J. (2016). Microstructural analysis of the cementation process during soiling on glass surfaces in arid and semi-arid climates. *physica status solidi (RRL)—Rapid Research Letters*, *10*(7), 525-529.
- Ilse, K. K., Figgis, B. W., Naumann, V., Hagendorf, C., & Bagdahn, J. (2018). Fundamentals of soiling processes on photovoltaic modules. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *98*, 239-254.
- Isaifan, R. J., Samara, A., Suwaileh, W., Johnson, D., Yiming, W., Abdallah, A. A., Assia, B. (2017). Improved self-cleaning properties of an efficient and easy to scale up TiO₂ thin films prepared by adsorptive self-assembly. *Sci Rep*; *7*, 9466.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-07826-0>.
- Jentsch, P. V., Kampe, B., Ciobotă, V., Rösch, P., & Popp, J. (2013). Inorganic salts in atmospheric particulate matter: Raman spectroscopy as an analytical tool. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, *115*, 697-708.
- Javed, W., Guo, B., & Figgis, B. (2017). Modeling of photovoltaic soiling loss as a function of environmental variables. *Solar Energy*, *157*, 397-407.
- Javed, W., Wubulikasimu, Y., Figgis, B., & Guo, B. (2017). Characterization of dust accumulated on photovoltaic panels in Doha, Qatar. *Solar Energy*, *142*, 123-135.
- Kazem, H. A., & Chaichan, M. T. (2016). Experimental analysis of the effect of dust's physical properties on photovoltaic modules in Northern Oman. *Solar Energy*, *139*, 68-80.
- Kazem, H. A., Chaichan, M. T., Alwaeli, A. H., & Mani, K. (2017). Effect of shadows on the performance of solar photovoltaic. In *Mediterranean Green Buildings & Renewable Energy* (pp. 379-385). Springer, Cham.
- Kazem, A. A., Chaichan, M. T., & Kazem, H. A. (2014). Dust effect on photovoltaic utilization in Iraq. *Renewable and Sustainable energy reviews*, *37*, 734-749.

- Kazem, H. A., & Chaichan, M. T. (2015). Effect of humidity on photovoltaic performance based on experimental study. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research (IJAER)*, 10(23), 43572-43577.
- Kazem, H. A., Khatib, T., Sopian, K., & Elmenreich, W. (2014). Performance and feasibility assessment of a 1.4 kW roof top grid-connected photovoltaic power system under desertic weather conditions. *Energy and Buildings*, 82, 123-129.
- Kazem, H., Khatib, T., Sopian, K., Buttinger, F., Elmenreich, W., & Albusaidi, A. S. (2013). Effect of dust deposition on the performance of multi-crystalline photovoltaic modules based on experimental measurements. *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research (IJRER)*, 3(4), 850-853.
- Kazem, H. A. (2011). Renewable energy in Oman: Status and future prospects. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 15(8), 3465-3469.
- Kazem, H. A., & Khatib, T. (2013). Techno-economical assessment of grid connected photovoltaic power systems productivity in Sohar, Oman. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 3, 61-65.
- Lu, J., & Hajimirza, S. (2017). Optimizing sun-tracking angle for higher irradiance collection of PV panels using a particle-based dust accumulation model with gravity effect. *Solar Energy*, 158, 71-82.
- Lombardo, T., Ionescu, A., Chabas, A., Lefèvre, R. A., Ausset, P., & Candau, Y. (2010). Dose–response function for the soiling of silica–soda–lime glass due to dry deposition. *Science of the total environment*, 408(4), 976-984.
- Moharram, K. A., Abd-Elhady, M. S., Kandil, H. A., & El-Sherif, H. (2013). Influence of cleaning using water and surfactants on the performance of photovoltaic panels. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 68, 266-272.
- Miller, D. C., Muller, M. T., & Simpson, L. J. (2016). Review of Artificial Abrasion Test Methods for PV Module Technology. *Contract*.
- Nayshevsky, I., Xu, Q., Barahman, G., & Lyons, A. (2017). Anti-reflective and anti-soiling properties of KleanBoost™ a superhydrophobic nano-textured coating for solar glass. In *2017 IEEE PVSC-44*. IEEE Washington DC.
- Oguntoke, O., Ojelede, M. E., & Annegarn, H. J. (2013). Frequency of mine dust episodes and the influence of meteorological parameters on the Witwatersrand area, South Africa. *International Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 2013.
- Quan, Y. Y., & Zhang, L. Z. (2017). Experimental investigation of the anti-dust effect of transparent hydrophobic coatings applied for solar cell covering glass. *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, 160, 382-389.
- Saidan, M., Albaali, A. G., Alasis, E., & Kaldellis, J. K. (2016). Experimental study on the effect of dust deposition on solar photovoltaic panels in desert environment. *Renewable Energy*, 92, 499-505.
- Sarver, T., Al-Qaraghuli, A., & Kazmerski, L. L. (2013). A comprehensive review of the impact of dust on the use of solar energy: History, investigations, results, literature, and mitigation approaches. *Renewable and sustainable energy Reviews*, 22, 698-733.
- Saidan, M., Albaali, A. G., Alasis, E., & Kaldellis, J. K. (2016). Experimental study on the effect of dust deposition on solar photovoltaic panels in desert environment. *Renewable Energy*, 92, 499-505.

- Tanesab, J., Parlevliet, D., Whale, J., & Urmee, T. (2017). Seasonal effect of dust on the degradation of PV modules performance deployed in different climate areas. *Renewable Energy*, *111*, 105-115.
- Ta, W., Xiao, H., Qu, J., Xiao, Z., Yang, G., Wang, T., & Zhang, X. (2004). Measurements of dust deposition in Gansu Province, China, 1986–2000. *Geomorphology*, *57*(1-2), 41-51.
- Xu, R., Ni, K., Hu, Y., Si, J., Wen, H., & Yu, D. (2017). Analysis of the optimum tilt angle for a soiled PV panel. *Energy Conversion and Management*, *148*, 100-109.
- Yilbas, B. S., Ali, H., Khaled, M. M., Al-Aqeeli, N., Abu-Dheir, N., & Varanasi, K. K. (2015). Influence of dust and mud on the optical, chemical, and mechanical properties of a PV protective glass. *Scientific reports*, *5*, 15833.
- Zhong, H., Hu, Y., Wang, Y., Yang, H. (2017). TiO₂/silane coupling agent composed of two layers structure: a super-hydrophilic self-cleaning coating applied in PV panels. *Appl. Energy*; *204*, 932–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2017.04.057>.